

THE REFLECTION OF POST GLOBALIZATION TERMS ON GROWTH CENTRES DEVELOPMENT

Muhammad Abdul Rahman Seddeek

Research Scholar
Department of Geography
Andhra University, Visakhapatnam

Dr.T.V.Krishna

Professor
Department of Geography
Andhra University, Visakhapatnam

Abstract

The development of growth centres such as many terms needs to be changed to adapt to the process of globalization and post globalization. The main goal for the GCs development is to be sustainable and this is required to consider the dimensions of sustainability and execute the development process of four development stages which starting with the fundamental factors and ending with providing of innovations. Create of the competitiveness between the GCs, which in the same level as the global GCs distinguished than the national and regional one. However, the GCs level they need to be resilience especially in the economic shocks, this depends on some factors such as the government capacity and the infrastructure and natural resources development capacity. In addition, one of the main factor to achieve the economic reliance is the economic power, which needs Productive economic structure and increases the ability to attract foreign direct investment and on long run provide long-term planning. To have economic power the process of GCs development should seek to establish creative GCs; this needs a creative economic sector with distinctive advantages, which in turn will lead to competitiveness and economic power, and ending with sustainability.

Key Words:Growth centres (GCs) – Competitiveness - Global Economy - Resilience Economy - Economic power – Sustainability – Sustainable Regional Development (SRD)

INTRODUCTION

After emerging the process of globalization started from 1990 new development directions are needed to accommodate the rapid economic growth and fast economic changes. Growth centers despite implementation decline by the end of the eighties but still a valid policy to develop the backward regions but to get high economic performance the GCs should adopt with the new globalization process.

Whether the growth centres emerging in developed or developing countries to keep on the development indicators as targeted state should develop them in an atmosphere of sustainability, competitiveness, creativity, high level of productivity and maintain them always to have the proper economic power.

1. Growth centres in the concepts of sustainability

The sustainable development of countries, regions, and cities does not depend exclusively on the level of savings and investment in each economy, but mainly on the functioning of

the forces that condition capital accumulation and economic development (Antonio, 2007). AbdulRahman, 2012 mentioned that the sustainable regional development is aimed for improving the sustainability of the economic, social, urban and environmental sectors within a specific region and within the framework of a national plan for sustainable development that sets out its general indicators, the size of its investment and the most important required developmental sectors.

Growth centres can help in achieving this, as it is the container for the economic development and easily can follow the accumulation of the capital and its reflection on the human development enhancement.

1.1 Reflecting the concept of sustainable development on the planning of growth centers (AbdulRahman, 2012):

- Increase the capacity to good use of regional resources and improving human capital.
- Developing the centres with their resources and possibilities to achieve maximum efficiency.
- Provide environmental protection, which is a common resource among all communities and regions.
- Encourage people to work together to maintain natural resources, create jobs and raise the quality of life.
- Empower rural and urban communities within the centre periphery to make sustainable development by providing the necessary tools.
- Continuous use of renewable sources of surface resources, living organisms and terrestrial resources for the conservation of biological diversity.
- Reduce environmental degradation and pollution levels in urban areas.
- Reducing the effects of natural disasters.
- Significant improvements in the lives of slum dwellers.
- Providing housing and infrastructure in urban areas, especially for marginalized social groups.
- Improving the quality of health services and achieving full access of citizens to health services and improving the quality and accessibility of education.
- Rationalize and improve the selection of development sites.
- Support sustainable transport and sustainable development and urban planning.
- Sustainable management of solid waste.

1.2 Considerate dimensions when planning growth centers to achieve sustainability (AbdulRahman, 2012):

Integration: The GCs are concerned with the integration and interaction between development sites and their inputs in the social, urban, economic, and environmental sectors in one hand, in the other hand between the centre and its periphery.

Homogeneity: focusing on the formation of successful relationships between the population and nature, with the economic and business areas.

Participation; The process of consultation and participation of the community, public and private sector and non-profit civil society organizations to identify the activities and requirements required by growth centre.

Flexibility with the fast changes: As a result of globalization and the speed of information circulation and the freedom of capital and technology, the GCs has become economically open, which led to increased input and output in the development process.

The shift in the development level: The growth centres can move from a development level to another, depending on its acquisition of regional and global competitiveness.

The adoption of innovation: the introduction and diffusion of innovations and knowledge leads to improvement in the stock of technological knowledge of the productive system, which creates external economies, for the benefit of all sorts of firms in the system (Antonio, 2007).

1.3 Sustainable growth centres' characteristics

1.3.1 Urban characteristics

- The spread of urban densities in a balanced manner at the level of GC to achieve the principles of population redistribution advocated by SRD.
- A clear inclusion in the network of urban and rural-urban communities within the hinterland and avoid the overlapping with other domains growth centre in respect of the concept of sustainable management and good internal governance.
- An active role for socially marginalized groups.
- Respect the separation areas and protection between the urban areas, which fall under the names of several green areas, green belts or may be in forests and large parks.
- It is characterized by high rates of access to services, which respects the thought of the absorptive capacity of each service to play its role in an integrated and that there is a continuous vision of the expansion and development, which are consistent with the opportunities for economic and urban growth and population allowed in GCs.
- Availability of absorption future urban areas to maintain the urban carrying capacity of the existing urban architecture, and keep it under the allowed levels.

1.3.2 Economic characteristics

- Low inflation rates and rise in the GDP index compared to the region or the state.
- A high rate of employment generation against the increase of non-polluting economic projects.
- There are no economic restrictions on the movement of goods from and to the growth centre (free trade) as long as these goods are subject to environmental control and pass the standards of health.
- Depends on the local resources in manufacturing and production within the centre's periphery and the development of internal investment and increase the support of domestic resources in the industry as long as these resources are not polluted and harmless to the vital system.
- Depends on the production of local food as long as the needs of the population and as long as the environmental surveys regarding the volume of organic and fertilizers.

1.3.3 Social characteristics:

- Decrease the poverty rate of the population of the GCs' area compared to the national and regional level and work to develop these rates constantly to eradicate the poverty.
- Protect heritage areas and communities with historical value of local communities in the GCs' area and support them in various economic, urban and cultural fields.
- Increase the expected age of both sexes and reach the global average.
- High rates of health care and the availability of basic health services for all communities in the growth centre's area as a whole.

1.4 Stages of developing the growth centers for sustainability

1.4.1 Development phase driven by fundamental factors:

This is considered as the fundamental stage, and whenever investment are high, it will lead to the establishment of a robust physical infrastructure with a range of institutions that will support a healthy start of growth centre at the regional or national level according to the target development plan.

The diversity of institutions between government and private institutions with other NGOs gives a strong start to the growth center where institutional diversity will be reflected in the diversity of the economic sector and the diversity of economic visions aimed at achieving future economic growth. Human capital is one of the most important factors that must be prepared for the labor market in line with the requirements of the local and regional economy. None of the above will work without a distinct level of security as capital always escapes from troubled areas. Security will protect the entire social and economic system and will lead to stability at the macro level, whether in the growth center or its region.

1.4.2 Development Stage driven by efficiency:

The second phase is extremely important; the efficiency of the markets created as a result of the initial phase must be maintained and supported. Market efficiency means activating markets, creating new marketing policies and introducing continuous incentive policies for the product and the consumer. Indeed, the process of continuing to development requires continued capital efficiency. This occurs at the level of the growth center by stimulating investment opportunities and creating tax-incentive policies. Continuing studies of the capital cycle and how to re-employ them optimally will lead to the efficiency of the economic sector that supports the growth of the center in the end.

1.4.3 Development driven by innovations:

With the passage of time and the relative equilibrium in the size and saturation of markets, there should be an assessment of all the previous stages and compared to the desired situation. Often, growth centers tend to the recession and if not dealt with will lead to decaying at the macro level. Dealing with the decaying is through technological development and allowed for more creativity at the level of different economic sectors.

Markets need to be more open to accommodate with diverse technological changes. The industries and the leading economic sectors should also be more ready to initiate technical and technical developments to ensure continuity in the production of competitive products.

From the last stage, which seek to help the GCs to continue developing, we can say that the competitiveness of the RGCs is one of the requirements of sustainable development. Competitiveness is the ability to achieve long-term prosperity while maintaining the productivity and quality of life of society and is reflected in the urbanization.

2. Growth centres in the concepts of competitiveness

The principles of competitiveness indicates logically that any center, need to maintain a competitive advantage; however, the centre is small or significant in size, it should use the advantages to create competitive development process (Wakeley, 1962). The concept of competitiveness should introduce in the growth centres in a comprehensive sense. Competitiveness is an integrated system with main goal to raise the standard of living of the individual through policies and trends that take into consideration economic, social, environmental and other aspects. For the development of all the different sectors, in light of the maintenance and upgrading of environmental components (AlBashir, 2014). The vast difference between the GCs in the traditional and competitive development is the factors of production depend on the static factors like (Local resources, local labor. etc.), while in the competitive sense is due mainly to dynamism production factors.

2.1 Growth center requirements to be dynamic and competitive

2.1.1 Competitive advantage location

- The regional growth center selection site should have competitive advantage factors to ensure the competitiveness of growth factors in the regional context, as follows:
 - The regional cities are experiencing dynamics growth are quite distinct from both the primary metropolitan centres and smaller rural localities, with significant implications for policy planning also amongst the state's regional cities with some performing far better than others (Plummer et al., 2014).
 - GCs connecting to the roads networks and transport means and communication.
 - Population and population density matching the economic threshold to emerge proper markets.
 - The availability of natural resources and the future development potential of the GCs and its periphery.
 - Whether large and medium-sized GCs should consider the carrying capacity and taking advantage of the economic and economic savings available to them.
- Utilizing the economic resources available in the provincial capitals and the administrative centers and directing them to the development of the GCs' areas.
- The formation of a balanced urban system consisting of multi-level growth centers (national, regional and local) to integrate their functions and economic activities following the past and present development realities and the expected future role.
- Integration between the urbanization system and the natural environment and taking into consideration the protection of the environment and reduce pollution and benefit from natural resources within the framework of sustainable development.

2.1.2 A unique and innovative operating environment to develop and attract factors of production and investments.

This there is no doubt that factors of production are the necessary inputs needed to support industry's ability to compete. These factors take the traditional form (natural resources including arable land, labor, and capital) as well as infrastructure.

It is imperative to have a local demand and work on developing it, which of course will help in sustaining the economic demand for the regional growth center. It should be noted, there is a follow-up to the pressure generated by the increase in domestic demand, which may lead to the acceleration of growth in the RGCs and here clearly shows the role of governance in the careful planning of GCs and taking into account future growth paths to deal with the expected demand for economic activities.

2.1.3 Collecting and gathering investment activities.

The related industries (complementary) and supporting industries plays crucial key to gathering the investments in the growth centre and its periphery which is active in receiving the complementary industries through good connectivity to the roads and communication network.

Feeding and complementary industries are the reason for the success of many industries and activities. They are able in competitiveness because they are intertwined with each other in technologies, inputs and distribution channels, which contributes to the degree of development and the creation of better production and management skills.

2.1.4 Establishment of the industrial clusters

Firms or enterprises cannot in any way achieve competitive advantage through their presence in individual industries, but they can achieve this advantage by connecting with other local facilities that are efficient in other feeder and related industries. This means that the presence of industries as part of clusters is an important and fundamental factor and is even one of the most important factors in achieving competitive advantage.

Porter, 1998 believes that competition is affected by the presence of these clusters by increasing the productivity of the cluster organizations and increasing their capacity to innovate new cluster.

2.1.5 Constant government role to develop competitiveness of activities.

The government has an important role to keep on the competitiveness of activities within the growth centre. At the level of factors of production, the government can improve and develop these factors through its efforts to increase Productivity by increasing investments in education and training programs and linking them to the industrial reality and follow policies that lead to increased saving and investment promotion, the efficiency of investment allocation between different uses. Also, support and encourage development and innovation, availability of data and statistics and increase investment in infrastructure.

Government policies can also affect the enterprise strategy and structure, and has the responsibility to establish specialized training centers, establish research programs in universities for cooperation between institutions and universities, and others.

3. Growth centres in the global economy

In the open global economy, there is a significant role of international trade in the economic growth. This form of growth also happens because of the next factors:

- Many knowledge spillovers occur within very concentrated economic regions—clusters and districts within cities.
- Institutional effects operate partly at the national level but also at the level of provinces, cities, or special economic zones.
- A city or country that offers high returns to firms or workers will attract inflows of these factors more than the others will.

Depending on that, the speed and level of growth are not same at all centres in each country, there are multi-levels of growth centres:

- Global growth centres, National growth centres, Regional growth centres, and Local growth centres.

3.1 The global growth centres,

Dobrescu & Dobre, 2014 define the global GCs due to the quantitative contribution of the economy leading to global growth, supported by the power of internal links.

Zhang, 2013, mentioned that Sassen, 1991 distinguishes 'global cities' from 'world cities' and insists that global cities are a new type of economic co-ordinating unit, specific to the era of globalization, these cities do not merely compete with each other, but function as one trans territorial marketplace. These cities function similarly as international financial centres, with an intensive concentration of a wide variety of foreign commercial businesses and transactions enjoying both agglomeration and scale economies in financial transactions. The global GCs having advantages based on innovation and more complex skills and technology that are locally synthesized.

Growth centers requirements to enter the global economy:

- GCs should have exposure to national and foreign trade.
- GCs should have natural resources for exports or natural advantages, such as proximity to rivers, coasts, and transportation networks.
- Should have economic investment policy in response to the globalization challenges.
- High levels of investments in infrastructures (such as international airports, ports, roads, underground, high-speed railways).
- Incorporate in their plan different attractive advantages to inward investment and global capital.
- Should have strategy to reduce production costs of up to a deregulation of the labor.
- The structure of industries should group itself into multi-clusters.
- The economic structure should have value chain. The value chain is defined as a sequence of activities to create a valuable product on the market and thereby create value (Dobrescu & Dobre, 2014).
- Involves strategies of quality and innovation to create new products.
- Should have competitiveness clusters that must meet the "next status": "Representing a combination of a given geographical area, businesses, training centers and public or private research units, engaged in a partnership approach for to create synergies around common projects of an innovative nature" (Dobrescu & Dobre, 2014).

3.2 National growth centres

National GCs shows the desire and ability of the state and its companies to invest continuously, investing in modern production facilities, and technical development in these centers not only to apply foreign technologies but also to improve them. Developing the conditions of productive factors, investment and the strategy of the state and the economic structure and the nature of competition in the domestic market.

Domestic demand is complex, and the related industries are not well developed. The economy is successful in industries characterized by high domestic demand. These centers are developing when the supply side is attracting demand.

The national GCs' economic sectors should enjoy reasonable levels of technology. The availability and use of information and communication technologies are a prerequisite for economic and social development at that level. It is essential for the national GCs of being connected to the regional and global networks to speed up development.

3.4 Regional growth centres

The RGCs operate at the level of the broader region, where the state is divided into a group of regions representing each region as a regional growth center. RGCs are characterized by support activities, namely inputs, technological development, human resources, infrastructure.

The RGCs are connected to a network of roads and transport at the level of the region to reach the local centers to ensure regional integration and exchange. If these networks managed efficiently and successfully, the GCs would be more competitive at the scale of the region. RGCs need an administrative structure capable of dealing with different economic networks and develop the future institutional dimensions.

RGCs are classified as centers with high population density and labor, according to (Brautigam & Manager, 2013); there is expected constant growth, which needs a plan to deal with the fast changes and high level of carrying capacities for the infrastructures.

3.5 Local growth centres "city-region" level

This level of GCs includes the primary activities of the necessity to establish local economic activity serves the regions and supports the exchange between the GCs and the periphery. These activities consist of internal transport, external transport, manufacturing, marketing, after-sale services. The economic structure is based on basic factors such as unskilled labor, land, geographical location, capital, and at this stage, the importance of other determinants of competitive advantage is diminished.

In addition being centers of economic growth, whether industrial or agricultural, these centers represent the regional base of services at the level of the city-region, where a series of trips to regional services are generated between the GCs and the settlements in the periphery. Many jobs are at the center of daily employment while living in rural or semi-urban communities in the periphery.

All the previous levels of growth centres under the fast and various challenges and changes in the globalization should perform their function under the concept of resilience economy.

4. Growth centres and the resilience economy

The notion of resilience is broadly defines as “a return to an original state”. The notion of resilience is rapidly becoming part of the conceptual and analytical of regional economic

studies, the resilience is a dynamic feature insured continuous regional development or fast enough recovery after the economic shock (Palekiene, et al. 2015).

The resilience defined as the ability of the system to anticipate, resist, absorb, respond to, adapt to, and recover from a disturbance. Resilience is determined how the region or system responds to shock or disturbance and under these circumstances able to ensure its continuous development.

Palekiene, et al. 2015 mentioned that Davies et al. (2010) remarked that growth centre or region's inherent factors regional resilience depends on hidden in economic strengths and weaknesses. Such factors as physical and human capital, competitiveness, innovation system, entrepreneurial culture, endowments in natural resources and physical capital, etc., play a significant role shaping regional resilience.

Palekiene, et al. 2015 built regional resilience factors model, which is easy to adjust them to work on the level of growth centres. These factors as following:

4.1 Growth centres' resilience factors

Government capacity: Political and economic stability; Regional financial stability; Local government efficiency and agility; Public and private sector transparent cooperation; An open and transparent institutional business environment; Bureaucratic procedures unencumbered business administration; The spirit of entrepreneurship.

Strategic insights capacity: Continuous economic growth; development vision for achieving consistency; the economic integrity and openness; investment attractiveness; purchasing power and the level of material well-being.

Knowledge and innovation capacity: Business and government investment in research and innovation; Business and Science active co-operation; Innovation support services system functionality and availability; Intellectual property protection level of development; A positive attitude towards research and innovation.

Learning capacity: Developed and accessible science and education, lifelong learning and continuous improvement systems; Labor market flexibility and competence; Orientation on professionalism and quality.

Networking and cooperation capacity: Cooperation and feedback opportunities and intensity between government, business and research institutions; the involvement in international and national networks; Integration into the international and national value chains; Level of computer literacy and Internet use intensity; Various e-services availability.

Infrastructure and natural resources development capacity: Internet connection availability; Implementation of sustainable development principles for regional growth; Real estate, infrastructure availability level; pollution; accessibility by land/ air; Energy independence and quality of supply.

One of the resilience factors, which help the growth centres to stand against the economic shocks, is having the economic power. The need of economic power will discuss in the next paragraphs.

5. Growth centres with economic power

According to Poladian & Oehler-Şincai, 2014 the economic power is characterized by several elements: resources or potential of leadership (population, area, natural resources, technological progress, education, economic and military strength and political stability).

The spatial dimension (the geographical area of the exercise of power, regionally or globally) and status (recognition, whether formal or informal, of its leadership).

5.1 Elements of the economic power:

Productive economic structure: productivity is related to population concentration. More than half of the world's population is now living in towns and cities. Underpinning this transformation are the economies of scale that make concentrated urban centers more productive.

Preferences granted by the central government: the government could grant attractive policies, for example, Special Economic Zone, this will help to elevate the history and location and economies of scale to competitive way.

The ability to attract foreign direct investment (FDI): larger cities have opportunities to land it in their economic structure. The establishment of a foreign-invested community reduces perceived investment risks and creates a virtuous cycle that serves to attract more investment in the future.

Located in cities cluster: City network effects stimulate economic growth. Large cities are usually at the center of a cluster of smaller cities, and network effects spur economic growth and productivity.

Provide long planning: the growth centres are highly complex and demanding environments that require a long planning horizon and extraordinary managerial skills.

ensure competitiveness: the creation of the competitiveness depend on different factors, the most important is the population size, McKinsey Global Institute, 2011 mentioned that larger cities have been more competitive than smaller ones in the provision of these benefits and others that are favorable to businesses.

Plan to cope with the risk of diseconomies; many governments are not prepared to cope with the speed at which their populations are growing. Without skillful plan and management, cities run the risk of diseconomies— such as congestion and pollution— starting to outweigh scale benefits, leading to a deteriorating quality of life and a loss of economic dynamism.

The ability to keep on affordable housing stock: emerging cities will be home to a growing number of households in the consuming and global categories.

6. Growth centres as creative centres

The creative economy is known in the literature mainly as the production of creative industries as Media, Crafts/jewelry, Fashion, Arts, and Advertising, etc. recently add to this list the knowledge industries and innovations. In particular, the shift from the arts, heritage and cultural industries towards the creative industries and from the cultural and creative city to the wider knowledge city —and the spatial representation in cultural quarters, creative clusters, media parks and science 'cities' (Cooke and Lazeretti, 2008).

At the level of growth centre the research mean with the creative centres is the ability to develop within the atmosphere of competitiveness and the ability to sustain the economic activities by attracting new investment whether local or foreign.

6.1 The creative growth centre

whether the central core and the periphery is consonant with area-based regeneration, business improvement districts, heritage and conservation and zoning strategies, which neatly attempt to square what is fundamentally global strategic growth arguments driven

by national, supranational and regional authorities, with local impacts and governance implications (Evans, 2009). Emerging cities using the cultural and creative economy as a growth strategy. This is manifested in both employment and GDP contribution to regional and national economies, but also in the extent of 'creative class' presence in primarily central-core and growth centre periphery (Evans, 2009).

6.2 Elements of the creative growth centre;

- The emphasis on the role SMEs to change the image of the traditional economy.
- Using social regeneration and local economy at the cost of larger creative sectors.
- Expand reliance on creative/knowledge economy and clusters, which account for the growth performance.
- Using culture, and cultural industries as instruments of the nation-state (such as broadcasting, arts, and heritage), to the more global creative industries.
- Widely use the industries that have their origin in individual creativity, skill, and talent and which have the potential for wealth and job creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property (Evans, 2009).
- Growth centres and regional authorities have policy and programs to promote creative and knowledge industries status.
- Establish regional industrial clusters, in new economic areas within the growth center region where multiple or polycentric clusters and networks.

Conclusion

The process of GCs development aims to achieve sustainability on the short and long-term and to be sustainable GCs needs to consider the sustainable framework and create sustainable planning factors. Classifying the GCs using their developmental level helping in determine the proper requirements as the global level needs different growth and development factors than the national and regional level. To plan the GCs to sustainable the economic structure should be remarked with economic powers and have creative economic sectors. If any economic structure has both advantages it will be more resilience comparing with other as in the globalization era, the changes become so fast and the economic shocks can destroy the static structure.

References

- AbdulRahman, M. (2012). Principles to achieve sustainability in the city regions development. Unpublished M.Sc thesis, Cairo University. (in Arabic)
- AlBashir, S. (2014). Formulating a competitive guide for urban development centers in Egypt. Unpublished M.Sc thesis, Cairo University. (in Arabic)
- Antonio V-B. (2007). Endogenous Development: Analytical and Policy issues. Development on the ground : clusters, networks and regions in emerging economies. London [u.a.] : Routledge. p. 23-43. ISBN 978-0-415-77118-4.
- Brautigam, J. S., & Manager, C. (2013). Station Area Transit-oriented Development Potential Report. Lynnwood Link.
- Cooke, P. & Lazeretti, L. (2008) Creative Cities, Cultural Clusters and Local

- Economic Development. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.
- Dobrescu, E. M., & Dobre, E. M. (2014). GROWTH POLES . RELATED CONCEPTS. *Knowledge Horizons - Economics*, 6(2), 17–20.
 - Evans, G. (2009). *Creative Cities, Creative Spaces and Urban Policy*. *Urban Studies* (Vol. 46). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098009103853>
 - McKinsey Global Institute. (2011). *Urban world: Mapping the economic power of cities*. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 36(March), 49. Retrieved from http://www.mckinsey.com/insights/urbanization/urban_world
 - Palekiene, O., Simanaviciene, Z., & Bruneckiene, J. (2015). The Application of Resilience Concept in the Regional Development Context. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 213, 179–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.423>
 - Plummer, P., Tonts, M., & Martinus, K. (2014). Local Competitiveness and Regional Development: Western Australia' s Regional Cities. *Journal of Economic and Social Policy*, 16(1), 2001–2011.
 - Poladian, S. M., & Oehler-Şincai, I. M. (2014). Emerging of New Poles of Economic Power in the World. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 8(14), 474–483. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(14\)00116-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(14)00116-6)
 - Porter, M. (1998). *Clusters and the New Economics of Competition*. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from <http://hbr.org/product/clusters-and-the-new-economics-of-competition/an/98609-PDF-ENG>
 - Wakeley, R. E. (1962). *Growth and Decline of Towns and Cities in Southern Illinois*. Southern Illinois University Carbondale OpenSIUC. Retrieved from http://opensiuc.lib.siu.edu/ua_docs
 - Zhang, L.-Y. (2013). Dynamics and Constraints of State-led Global City Formation in Emerging Economies: The Case of Shanghai. *Urban Studies*, 51(6), 1162–1178. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098013495577>